

INDEPENDENT LEARNING STRATEGIES AND THE SPEAKING SKILLS OF GRADE 11 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study focused in determining relationship between independent learning strategies and speaking skills of students in English. This study utilized descriptive-correlational research. One hundred ten (110) Grade 11 Humanities and Social Sciences students from Recto Memorial National High School were chosen as the respondents of the study using the stratified random sampling. The researcher-made instrument, consisting of two parts: frequency on the use of four independent strategies namely, goal setting, attention control, self-monitoring and evaluation, and help seeking and a 40-item test on the speaking skills particularly pronunciation, word stress, grammar and vocabulary, was used as the main data-gathering instrument. Preparatory measures were conducted before the implementation of the study; permission letters were also prepared and secured. The instrument have been validated and corrected by external and internal experts. The result of the variables showed independent learning strategies such as goal setting and attention control were found to be significantly correlated to speaking skills in English of the respondents in terms of pronunciation and vocabulary. However, the result also revealed that the independent learning strategies such as self-monitoring and evaluation and help seeking were found to have no significant relationship with the respondents' speaking skills in English.

Keywords: (a) independent learning strategies, speaking skills, (b) goal setting, attention control, self-monitoring and evaluation, help seeking, pronunciation, stress, grammar, vocabulary, (c) descriptive-correlational research, (d) Philippines